

Stage 2, bin no. 5, reconstruction: 525 Ma

Stage 3, bin no. 6, reconstruction: 515 Ma

Stage 4, bin no. 7, reconstruction: 510 Ma

Stage 5, bin no. 8, reconstruction: 505 Ma

Drumian, bin no. 9, reconstruction: 500 Ma

Guzhangian, bin no. 10, reconstruction: 500 Ma

Jiangshanian, bin no. 12, reconstruction: 490 Ma

Lawsonian, bin no. 13, reconstruction: 485 Ma

Tremadocian, bin no. 14, reconstruction: 480 Ma

Floian, bin no. 15, reconstruction: 475 Ma

Dapingian, bin no. 16, reconstruction: 470 Ma

Darriwilian, bin no. 17, reconstruction: 465 Ma

Sandbian, bin no. 18, reconstruction: 455 Ma

Katian, bin no. 19, reconstruction: 450 Ma

Hirnantian, bin no. 20, reconstruction: 445 Ma

Rhuddanian, bin no. 21, reconstruction: 440 Ma

Aeronian, bin no. 22, reconstruction: 440 Ma

Telychian, bin no. 23, reconstruction: 435 Ma

Sheinwoodian, bin no. 24, reconstruction: 430 Ma

Homerian, bin no. 25, reconstruction: 430 Ma

Gorstian, bin no. 26, reconstruction: 425 Ma

Ludfordian, bin no. 27, reconstruction: 425 Ma

Pridoli, bin no. 28, reconstruction: 420 Ma

Lochkovian, bin no. 29, reconstruction: 415 Ma

Pragian, bin no. 30, reconstruction: 410 Ma

Emsian, bin no. 31, reconstruction: 400 Ma

Eifelian, bin no. 32, reconstruction: 390 Ma

Givetian, bin no. 33, reconstruction: 385 Ma

Frasnian, bin no. 34, reconstruction: 375 Ma

Famennian, bin no. 35, reconstruction: 365 Ma

Tournaisian, bin no. 36, reconstruction: 355 Ma

Visean, bin no. 37, reconstruction: 340 Ma

Serpukhovian, bin no. 38, reconstruction: 325 Ma

Bashkirian, bin no. 39, reconstruction: 320 Ma

Moscovian, bin no. 40, reconstruction: 310 Ma

Kasimovian, bin no. 41, reconstruction: 305 Ma

Gzhelian, bin no. 42, reconstruction: 300 Ma

Asselian, bin no. 43, reconstruction: 295 Ma

Sakmarian, bin no. 44, reconstruction: 295 Ma

Artinskian, bin no. 45, reconstruction: 285 Ma

Kungurian, bin no. 46, reconstruction: 275 Ma

Roadian, bin no. 47, reconstruction: 270 Ma

Wordian, bin no. 48, reconstruction: 265 Ma

Capitanian, bin no. 49, reconstruction: 260 Ma

Wuchiapingian, bin no. 50, reconstruction: 255 Ma

Changhsingian, bin no. 51, reconstruction: 255 Ma

Induan, bin no. 52, reconstruction: 250 Ma

Olenekian, bin no. 53, reconstruction: 250 Ma

Anisian, bin no. 54, reconstruction: 245 Ma

Ladinian, bin no. 55, reconstruction: 240 Ma

Carnian, bin no. 56, reconstruction: 230 Ma

Norian, bin no. 57, reconstruction: 220 Ma

Rhaetian, bin no. 58, reconstruction: 205 Ma

Hettangian, bin no. 59, reconstruction: 200 Ma

Sinemurian, bin no. 60, reconstruction: 195 Ma

Pliensbachian, bin no. 61, reconstruction: 185 Ma

Toarcian, bin no. 62, reconstruction: 180 Ma

Aalenian, bin no. 63, reconstruction: 170 Ma

Bajocian, bin no. 64, reconstruction: 170 Ma

Bathonian, bin no. 65, reconstruction: 165 Ma

Callovian, bin no. 66, reconstruction: 165 Ma

Oxfordian, bin no. 67, reconstruction: 160 Ma

Kimmeridgian, bin no. 68, reconstruction: 155 Ma

Tithonian, bin no. 69, reconstruction: 150 Ma

Berriasian, bin no. 70, reconstruction: 140 Ma

Valanginian, bin no. 71, reconstruction: 135 Ma

Hauterivian, bin no. 72, reconstruction: 130 Ma

Barremian, bin no. 73, reconstruction: 125 Ma

Aptian, bin no. 74, reconstruction: 120 Ma

Albian, bin no. 75, reconstruction: 105 Ma

Cenomanian, bin no. 76, reconstruction: 95 Ma

Turonian, bin no. 77, reconstruction: 90 Ma

Coniacian, bin no. 78, reconstruction: 90 Ma

Santonian, bin no. 79, reconstruction: 85 Ma

Campanian, bin no. 80, reconstruction: 80 Ma

Maastrichtian, bin no. 81, reconstruction: 70 Ma

Danian, bin no. 82, reconstruction: 65 Ma

Selandian–Thanetian, bin no. 83, reconstruction: 60 Ma

Ypresian, bin no. 84, reconstruction: 50 Ma

Lutetian, bin no. 85, reconstruction: 45 Ma

Bartonian, bin no. 86, reconstruction: 40 Ma

Priabonian, bin no. 87, reconstruction: 35 Ma

Rupelian, bin no. 88, reconstruction: 30 Ma

Chattian, bin no. 89, reconstruction: 25 Ma

Lower Miocene, bin no. 90, reconstruction: 20 Ma

Middle Miocene, bin no. 91, reconstruction: 15 Ma

Upper Miocene, bin no. 92, reconstruction: 10 Ma

Pliocene, bin no. 93, reconstruction: 5 Ma

Pleistocene, bin no. 94, reconstruction: 0 Ma

Holocene, bin no. 95, reconstruction: 0 Ma

